

THE IMPORTANCE OF ECOLOGICAL FACTORS IN ECONOMIC RESTORATION

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Abstract. This article presents information about the importance of environmental factors in economic stabilization and its study. It is also noted that the importance of environmental factors in the economic stabilization of the region is extremely high.

Keywords: economy, environmental factors, ecological system, sustainable development.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ФАКТОРОВ В ВОССТАНОВЛЕНИИ ЭКОНОМИКИ

Аннотация. В данной статье представлена информация о значении экологических факторов в экономической стабилизации и ее изучении. Также отмечается, что значение экологических факторов в экономической стабилизации региона чрезвычайно велико.

Ключевые слова: экономика, экологические факторы, экологическая система, устойчивое развитие.

INTRODUCTION

Due to globalization, a lot of attention is being paid to the issue of development stabilization in the scientific literature of the world scale. It is necessary that the parameters of this problem always keep their importance, that is: 1) physical constant; 2) gene pool; 3) participation of all major ecosystems in the most ancient state; 4) human health. So, conservation of environmental factors is a component of this concept, as well as economic recovery.

The socio-economy of the regions of our country is determined by their natural and economic characteristics, and it determines the level of development of each region. At the present time, when economic reforms are intensifying, the scientific research conducted within the regions has great theoretical and practical importance. It is the regional characteristics that are considered important factors in the development of ways of efficient use of the resource potential of the region.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Human's labor activity is based on his relationship with nature. As a person affects nature, he adapts the natural environment to his needs and desires with the help of social media. With the passage of time, the growing needs of man and the development of production will put more and more needs and demands on nature. As a result of this, economic and social problems arise as a result of human influence on nature and its change.

Protection of ecological factors is carried out for two different purposes: 1) to ensure that such qualities of the environment remain unchanged; 2) balancing the productivity of useful plants and animals, as well as the stability of resources necessary for humans, their restoration and extraction; 3) what and how much to take from nature and what not to take is determined by modeling.

The purpose of population ecology is to clarify the cultural composition of sometimes conflicting exigencies, which allows to determine the environmental scales that provide the cultural norms of population development. If we assume that economic growth depends on the quality of the population, it becomes clear how urgent it is to solve this problem.

Despite the fact that the research in the field of population ecology has increased, many issues that need to be solved quickly are left aside. These are both the problem of environmental conditions, the issue of socio-biological adaptation of the population to the environment, and the "adaptation" of nature to the developing needs of society and the population.

RESULTS

In particular, the end of the 20th century - the beginning of the 21st century is the period when the pressure of the anthropogenic factor on nature increased as a result of the use of natural resources by mankind without following the above-mentioned laws of nature. There is such a condition in nature that the maximum use of natural resources not only leads to their depletion, but also causes a decrease in the quality of the product. It has a negative impact on the development of each region. It is impossible to achieve maximum quantity and high quality in one time. Today, the only way of sustainable economic development is to limit the use of land, water and other resources, with a deep understanding of the nature and economic conditions, and to prevent overpopulation and depletion of natural resources. In relation to wild nature, humanity should become a human being who acts rationally rather than mindlessly exploiting it. If this problem is solved on our planet, then we can talk about sustainable development in society.

The concept of sustainable development helps to ensure the economic, biological and ecological stability of the relationship between society and nature, which encourages people to be creative.

DISCUSSION

In the use of natural resources of Central Asia during the years of stagnation. Also, as a result of non-compliance with environmental conditions in agriculture, extensive development of agriculture, irregular use of land and water, are being reason for the drying up of the Aral Sea, which has a great impact on the ecosystem and economy of this region. The ecological system of the land, flora and fauna in the territory of the island is in deep crisis.

Hundreds of thousands of lands in the region are lying in ruins. The soil is infected with microorganisms that cause various diseases. The above-mentioned environmental factors have a negative impact on the economic development of this region, therefore, in order to create a sustainable economy in the region, it is necessary to pay special attention to the ecological condition of the region. Economic development of the economy depends on the following conditions:

1. Optimal use of natural resources.
2. Effective use of financial resources and accumulation.
3. Encouraging farmers who use natural resources.

It is appropriate to pay special attention to these environmental factors in the formation of economic stability in the republic.

CONCLUSIONS

In our opinion, the main principles of choosing a strategy for the socio-economic development of the region should be environmental limitation of economic and household requirements.

In the conditions of the market economy, the main condition for taking environmental requirements into account in economic management is their practical embodiment. This situation is easily resolved when planning centrally. In the period of market economy, when farming is

developing, rent, cooperation and other forms of private ownership are developing, environmental limitation can be implemented only through economic methods.

If we want to create economic stability, then we need to evaluate the specific characteristics of environmental factors through analysis and observation.

A) The value of ecology makes people satisfy the environmental demands of several hundreds and thousands of generations.

B) Ecological value is the result of many years of evolutionary cocktail of nature. This factor is a qualitative assessment of the eco-component.

C) Ecological value is higher than all economic values.

D) Ecological value is the core of economic value.

E) The ecological value of the natural ecosystem is much higher than the value of secondary ecotourism.

From the above, it can be concluded that in case of a deep analysis of the laws of nature, it is necessary to compare the cost of considerable damage with the cost of its protection and restoration. Also, it is appropriate to identify the damage caused in the protection of nature, to take it into account during the production process and to develop a complex of measures to prevent it.

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